
An assessment of the functions of code-switching and code-mixing in Radio and YouTube commercials

Mary Temiloluwa Oso^{1*},
Basheerat Damilola Jimoh⁴

^{1,2&4}Department of English, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria, aratmarie@gmail.com¹,
dipojoke@yahoo.com², basheeratd@gmail.com⁴

³Department of English Language and Literature, American University, Yola, Nigeria,
moses.achinihu@aun.edu.ng

*Corresponding author

Received: 11 July 2025 | Accepted: 16 August 2025 | Published: 07 October 2025

Abstract: The mixture of codes in advertisements is a linguistic practice done by advertisers to perform some socially motivated functions geared towards ensuring an effective dissemination of intended information about advertised products and services. The objective of this study is to interpret the functions of the code-switched expressions in the selected advertisement jingles. The primary source of data was drawn from 60 code-switched advertisement jingles collected from 30 radio commercials and 30 online advertisements on *YouTube*. The result showed that the 6 functions of code-switching by Appel and Muysken (2006) were performed which include Referential, Directive, Expressive, Phatic, Metalinguistic and Poetic Functions. Also, two other functions called Maintenance and Elaborative Functions were discovered in the study. All these functions enhanced the listeners' acceptability, understanding and positive disposal towards the products and services. It is recommended that advertisers employ code-switching and code-mixing in different advertising engagements so as to explore different functions that they can perform and ultimately guarantee a very successful transfer of information about products and services to the members of the society.

Keywords: Bi/Multilingualism, Code-mixing, Code-switching, Commercials, Functions

Biographical notes:

Dr. (Mrs) Mary Temiloluwa Oso obtained her B.A., M.A. and Ph.D. degrees in English Language from the Department of English, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria. She is a promising scholar of English Language who has a penchant for rigorous scholarly research which possesses thematic originality, innovative stance and serve as immense contribution to the field of Applied Linguistics, Sociolinguistics and English Grammar. She works as an astute English tutor and has published some articles both in the field of Applied Linguistics and Sociolinguistics which is her area of interest.

Prof. Emmanuel Taiwo Babalola is a distinguished Professor of English and presently the Head of Department of English, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife. He is an astute educator to the core having supervised many Masters and doctoral students to success. Widely travelled and highly cerebral, his academic publications have appeared in reputable journals in various countries of the world. His area of interest are English Grammar, Sociolinguistics and Contemporary English Usage.

Dr. Moses Chika. Christian-Achinihu is an Assistant Professor at the Department of English and Literature, and also doubles as Interim Director of Academic Registry at American University University of Nigeria, Yola. He is a researcher with an interest in the application of Systemic Functional Linguistics, (Critical) Discourse Analysis and Multimodal theories to interrogate an array of linguistics intersections: language in/of new media, digital practices and civic engagement; linguistics as/in social action/ digital activism; language and social crises; language and health discourse and corpus-based/ computational linguistics.

Mrs. Basheerat Damilola Jimoh is currently a doctoral student in the Department of English, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife where she also tutors the Use of English. she obtained her B.A (Ed.) and M.A. degrees in the same institution. She also teaches English as a subject in secondary schools and as a second language to undergraduates. Her research interests is in Phonetics and Phonology of English as a second language (ESL) with focus on Nigerian English Pronunciation Patters. She is also interested in Applied

Research Article: This article is published by *Jozac Publishers* in the *Journal of Languages, Linguistics and Literary Studies (JLLLS)*. This article is distributed under a Creative Common [Attribution \(CC BY-SA 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) [International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/). **Conflict of Interest:** The author/s declared no conflict of interest.

1. Introduction

Language is an important tool of communication in which human beings use to interact and communicate in the society. Anybody without access to language cannot lead a normal life and cannot attain self-actualization. It is a universal possession of human beings and a major distinguishing factor between people and lower animals (Ogunsiji, 2013). Language is also referred to as a code. In bi/multilingual societies, there exists two linguistic phenomena called code-switching and code-mixing. Code-switching is the alternation of two languages within a single discourse, sentence or constituent. Code-mixing is the mixing of two or more languages or language varieties in speech.

There are several presumptions about language acquisition that relate to children having access to multiple languages, and in these kinds of circumstances, code-mixing in young bilingual children becomes unavoidable, leading to the eventual emergence of mixed language utterances (Jayeola and Adeniyi, 2025). Many people attribute the emergence of this type of incidence to a combination of parental input and perhaps the presence of other bilingual speakers of the two languages in a communicative environment. Code-switching and code-mixing are common linguistic practices by bilingual speakers which occur in day-to-day human interaction. In the aspect of advertisement jingles, the occurrence of code-switching and code-mixing might be done unconsciously or consciously by the advertisers who would have reflected on the lyrics and message of the jingle and present it in a manner that can make diverse categories of listeners to be reached with the information of the jingle and in order to achieve the overall aim of persuading the audience to patronise their products and services. This study is significant because it examines how this linguistic and verbal skill is being displayed by the advertisers of the jingles to effectively pass across their intended messages to listeners purposely achieve some socially motivated functions using Appel and Musyken's (2006) functions of code-switching as a theoretical framework. Therefore, this paper seeks to interpret the functions of the code-switched and code-mixed expressions in the selected jingles.

2. Literature review

2.1. An overview of code-switching and code-mixing

Code-switching is not a new linguistic behaviour among human beings. In fact, it is a popular phenomenon among the bilingual and multilingual speakers in Nigeria. It is regarded as a natural consequence of bilingualism and even the highest level of bilingualism (Bamisaye, 2007 and Babalola & Taiwo, 2009). Code-switching can be discussed from two different perspectives the functional and formal perspectives (Akindele & Adegbite, 1999). The formal type of code-switching refers to linguistic realisation of code-switching from one language to the other. Poplack (1980) has differentiated between the three types of code-switching. They are inter-sentential switching, intra-sentential switching and tag-switching. Sentences can be categorised according to their structural or semantic categories as well as their functions, according to Eleshin-Ajikobi (2025). The three types of code-switching are explained below.

- a.) Inter-sentential switching is described as the switch between clauses, sentence boundaries or sentence where one is in a language and the other in another language. Inter-sentential code-switching is also known as code-changing or simply code-switching (Ogunremi, 1992). Examples include:
 - i. The children went to school yesterday. *Nigbàti won de be, won le won pada.* (When they got there, they were sent back.)
This is English-Yorùbá code-switching.
 - ii. E no mata whether na im papa or mama, *he doesn't have regard for anyone.* (It doesn't matter if it is his father of mother, he doesn't have regard for anyone.)
This is Naija-English code-switching.
- b.) Intra-sentential switching refers to the switching that occurs inside the same clause or sentence which then contains elements of both languages. Intra-sentential code-switching is referred to as code-mixing (Lanz, 2011), language mixing, language interlarding (Ogunsiji, 2013) or language hybridisation. Examples include:
 - iii. Mo so fun e pe ko *stop* lati maa *behave* ni ona ti ko *make sense.*
(I told you that you should stop behaving in a senseless way.)
This is Yorùbá -English code-mixing.
 - iv. The man told me to *yan* my mind.
(The man told me to say my mind).
This is English-Naija code-mixing.
 - v. Tag switching is simply the insertion of a tag from one language into a sentence of another language. Tag switching is referred to as emblematic switching (Hoffman, 1991) or insertional code-switching (Toribio, 2001). Examples in tag-switching include the following:
 - vi. You wan marry my pikin, *àbí?*
(You want to marry my child, isn't it?)
This is Pidgin-Yorùbá tag switching.
 - vii. *Actually*, omo yen se nnkan to dun mi gan.
(Actually, that person did something that really pained me.)
This is Yorùbá-English tag switching.

2.2. Appel and Muysken's (2006) Functions of Code-switching

It is believed that code-switching and code-mixing used by the advertisers in the advertisement jingles occur to perform some functions. According to Appel and Musyken (2006), there are six functions of code-switching which are earlier stated in Appel and Musyken (1987). They include Referential function, Directive function, Expressive function, Phatic function, Metalinguistic function and Poetic function. These functions are explained by Appel and Musyken (1987 & 2006) below which are used to interpret the functions of code-switching performed in the code-switched, code-mixed and tag-switched expressions.

1. **Referential Function:** This type of function happens when the speaker uses code-switching due to ignorance or incompetence in that language regarding a certain subject. This is due to the fact that some concepts and expressions may not be present in the speaker's linguistic repertoire or the language itself, making the bilingual speaker to seek assistance in a different language. A specific word from a language may be semantically more appropriate for a given concept, which causes the speaker to switch to the language. Also, certain topics may be better discussed in one language. As a result, it is possible to say that all topic-related code-switching serves the referential function. The majority of bilingual speakers are aware of this referential function because, when asked why they switch, they typically respond that they are unable to use the appropriate words in one language, which makes them to use another.
2. **Directive Function:** This function directly affects the hearer or listener and can take many different forms. The first is to exclude some audience members from a certain conversational topic, and the alternative is to include a person by speaking in that person's language. Any switching that involves participants can be said to perform a directive function. A directive function is carried out when a speaker adopts a person's language to identify or associate with them. The directive function of code-switching basically aims to bring people into a conversation by using a familiar language (Appel & Muysken 2006). According to Rusli et al. (2018), speakers use the directive function as a communication technique to foster or preserve unity.
3. **Expressive Function:** This function occurs when speakers use two languages to emphasize their mixed identity. This function comes to play when speakers use more than a language to indicate and empower their self-identity and express and demonstrate their feelings (Rusli et al., 2018). Yankova and Vassileva (2013) opined that the expressive function of code-switching does not modify the meaning of what is being said, but provide additional information pertaining to speakers' or listeners' emotions or attitudes.
4. **Phatic Function:** This code-switching serves to indicate a change in the tone of the conversation and highlighting some pieces of information in the conversation. A code-switching activity that carries phatic function would involve a change in intonation that stresses the important parts of a conversation (Rusli et al., 2018). A speaker can use code-switching to lay emphasis on some important words or statements in the utterance.
5. **Metalinguistic Function:** This function occurs when it is used to comment directly or indirectly on the languages involved. A metalinguistic function of code-switching is established when speakers switch between different codes to dazzle the other participants with a display of linguistic expertise (Myers-Scotton, 1979). The metalinguistic function includes the use of quotations, phrases, and metaphors (Gumperz, 1982). A speaker would want to make a direct comment on the topic at hand in order to achieve this. According to Appel and Musyken (1987), performers, circus directors, and market vendors use the metalinguistic function to amaze others with their in-depth linguistic knowledge and skills.
6. **Poetic Function:** When code-switching involves the use of puns, jokes, rhymes, it is said to perform a poetic function. This is when words, funny phrases or jokes are used in various languages to serve entertainment purposes (Rusli et al., 2018). Chan (2009) suggested that code switching acts as a poetic device when words in various languages rhyme with each other and create a harmony sound.

2.3. Review on the Functions of Code-switching and Code-mixing in Advertisement Jingles

Studies on code-alternation has also been done in advertisement jingles/commercials in various countries of the world like Indonesia, Pakistan, Philippines, India, Egypt, Japan, Taiwan, Korea, Saudi Arabia etc. Advertisement jingles and commercials are broadcast on radio and television and are sometimes shared on online platforms like YouTube, Snapchat etc.

In Indonesia, Mulyanto et al. (2023), Girsang (2015), Muslimah et al. (2016), Kartika (2017), Rosmiaty et al. (2020), Mainake (2021), Herman et al. (2022), Fitri and Pamungkas (2023) and Wirajaya et al. (2023) carried out studies on code-switching and code-mixing in advertisement jingles and commercials in which they examined how Indonesian and its other regional languages like Javanese, Betawi and Sudanese are used with English. The use of Indonesian and its regional languages in the advertisements is used to reach a larger number of consumers and create solidarity and emotive connection between the products and services and the consumers. In the same vein, the use of English in the advertisements gives a modern and international outlook to the products and services. The use of Indonesian and English also bridges the communication barriers between the advertisers and the consumers.

The reasons for using the linguistic phenomena are to speak about a specific topic, express solidarity and empathy, to show emotions, use of repetition to clarify and make the message effectively communicated, to express group identity, to quote somebody, for the purpose of making the speakers' messages well understood, facility of expression, addressee specification, personalization and objectification and qualifying message. Other motivations for code-switching are to enhance the products' appeal and attractiveness, for price increase and to attract the customers'

attention and interest in the advertised products. Also, in the advertisements, there are different functions of code-alternation which include referential function, expressive function, phatic function, metalinguistic function, poetic function.

Furthermore, in Pakistan, Khan (2014), Riaz (2019) and Amjad and Rehman (2020) also carried out studies on language alternation in advertisement jingles and commercials in which they examined how language alternation of Urdu and English are used in commercials, its functions and impact on the audience. They found out that Urdu is undergoing language enrichment because code-oscillation and code-interlarding are frequently used with English, the modern language in advertisements. This linguistic practice reveals the likeness of the advertisers to be associated with English, the language of prestige, modernity and sophistication and it also creates a desire in people of lower and middle classes to increase their social affluence and become part of the upper class by buying the brands embellished with English words. It was also discovered that some Urdu words that have equivalents are forgotten or not employed but replaced with English words in the bid of make the message to be more interesting and grab the listeners' attention.

In the Philippines, Gocheco (2013), Tajolosa (2013), Banatao and Malenab-Temporal (2018) and Garcia (2020) also carried out researches on these linguistic phenomena of language oscillation and interlarding in advertisement jingles to examine how Filipino, Tagalog and English are used in these TV commercials, the types of code-switching used, its motivations and functions. It was discovered that the intra-sentential code-switching is the dominant type among others and code-oscillation was found to enhance memorability and high retention of information and also help to construct social identities which the audience can understand and associate with. Also, the motivations for using code-switching are used to cater for lack of language facility, to create bilingual puns, for language specificity, to command, to economise language due to time limit of the adverts, for euphemistic use of words so as to say them in an acceptable way to reduce embarrassment, for artistic/stylistic purposes and to express multiple identities. The functions performed by code-switching in the adverts are to persuade the audience, to inform, describe, explain, name, assert, advise or prescribe; to illustrate and ask rhetorical question.

In India, code-alternation is also studied in advertisement jingles. Barnali (2017) and Singh and Mishra (2021) also did justice to this by examining code-switching and code-mixing in TV commercials on YouTube. It was discovered that Hindi and English are frequently used in the advertisements and the intra-sentential code-switching is the prominent type of code-switching used in the advertisements. The effects of using code-switching and code-mixing in the advertisements is that they make the jingle to be beautiful, pleasant, captivating and helps the audience to commit to memory the commercials with ease, thereby enabling an effective communication. Code-interlarding is also a valuable means of making the language more effective when advertising because it has the ability to attract the attention of the audience and persuade them through the attractive and amusing code-mixing patterns to think and act positively.

In countries like Egypt and Saudi Arabia, code-switching and code-mixing have also been studied in advertisement jingles and commercials to examine how Arabic, its varieties and English are used (Younes, 2017; Almoaily, 2020). Also, in Taiwan, Hsu (2008) and Chiu (2012) have examined how Taiwanese, Mandarin and Chinese are used with foreign languages like English, Japanese and German. In addition to this, Japan and Korean are not left out in this study of code-switching and code-mixing in advertisement jingles and commercials to examine how Japanese, Kansai dialect is used with English and Chinese in Japan and how Korean and English are used in Korea (Lee, 2006; Raden et al., 2022). From these reviews, different functions of code-switching were discovered in these studies.

3. Objectives of the study

The objective of this study is to interpret the functions of the code-switched, code-mixed and tag-switched expressions in the selected Southwestern Nigerian Radio advertisement jingles and Online advertisement jingles.

3.1 Research Questions

The paper intends to answer these research questions:

- i. What are the functions performed by the code-switched, code-mixed and tag switched expressions in the advertisement jingles?
- ii. Are the six functions of code-switching by Appel and Musyken (2006) performed by the code-switched, code-mixed and tag switched expressions in the advertisement jingles?
- iii. Are there other functions of code-switching performed by the code-switched, code-mixed and tag switched expressions which are different from Appel and Musyken (2006) functions of code-switching?

4. Methodology

The design of the study is qualitative because the functions of the code-switched, code-mixed and tag-switched expressions performed by the advertisement jingles are interpreted and discussed. The primary data is drawn from sixty (60) code-switched advertisement jingles which are collected from some selected Southwestern Nigerian radio and online advertisement jingles from YouTube. From the 6 Southwestern states in Nigeria which are Osun, Oyo, Ondo, Ogun, Ekiti and Lagos, 12 radio stations are randomly selected. In each of the 6 states, a private radio station and a public radio station are randomly selected which makes a total of 12 radio stations. The radio stations include Cool FM and Bond FM (Lagos), Splash FM and Paramount FM (Ogun), Crown FM and Orisun FM (Osun), Splash FM and Amuludun FM (Oyo), Adaba FM and Orange FM (Ondo) and lastly New Cruse and Ekiti FM (Ekiti). The jingles selected from both sources are limited to jingles advertising products and services.

The sampling technique used in the collection of the data for the study is a purposive random sampling technique. This sampling technique is chosen because there are some criteria guiding the data collection so as to fulfill the purpose of the study. The first criterion is that the jingles must be rendered in more than one language which is restricted to Yorùbá, Naija and English and the second criterion is that the advertisement jingles are either advertising consumer products, business services or personal services.

5. Data Analysis

From the analysis of the instances of Inter-sentential Code-switching (henceforth ICS), Intra-sentential Code-switching or code-mixing (ICM) and Tag switching (TGS) in the advertisement jingles, it was discovered that the code-switched, code-mixed and tag switched expressions used by advertisers perform all the functions of code-switching according to Appel and Muysken's (2006) functions of code-switching. Also, in some code-switched and code-mixed expressions, more than one function is performed. Also, two other new functions were uncovered during the analysis. These functions are examined below:

5.1 Referential function

The referential function is performed only in intra-sentential code-switching in some code-mixed expressions. Some examples of code-mixed expressions performing referential functions are seen below.

a. Referential functions are performed to cater for the unavailability or lack of facility in the Yorùbá language to express some words and concepts which make advertisers to borrow from English. The borrowed English words are emboldened in the Yorùbá sentences which can be seen below.

ICM 1 *9mobile máa sá o ní **data** òfè tó tó oḡófà **gigabyte** sínú èyíkéyìì **smartphone** tóo bá rà.*
(9mobile will give you free data up to 120 gigabytes in any kind of smartphone you have bought.)
(9mobile, Amuludun FM, Oyo State)

ICM 2 *CoMalart la sè pèlú àpapò **artemether** àti **lumefantrine** láti dojúkò ibà tó wà lára, yòò sì paná rẹ̀ ní kíákíá.*
(CoMalart is made with the combination of artemether and lumefantrine to combats malaria that is in the body and it will subdue it.)
(CoMalart, YouTube)

b. Referential functions are performed to cater for the inadequacy of the Yorùbá translated versions or equivalents of some words or concepts by using their English versions that the listeners are likely familiar with which enables an easy and straightforward comprehension of the words when compared to their Yorùbá translated versions. The English words performing this function are emboldened in some code-mixed expressions which are found below.

ICM 1 *Oḡbón kún oḡbón, òye kún òye nínú imò **ICT** fún àwọn akèkòḡ tí yòò mú wọn dúró láàyè ara wọn, Oṣenífújà ní kí ẹ̀ máa bọ̀ o.*
(For added wisdom and more understanding in ICT for students that will make them to be independent, come to Openifuja.)
(Openifuja Advanced Technology, New Cruise FM, Ekiti State)

ICM 2 *Kòmáláàti o, Kòmáláàti o, ògùn **malaria** tó dára fún gbogbo ẹ̀bí.*
(CoMalart, CoMalart, malaria drug that is good for the whole family.)
(CoMalart, YouTube)

c. Referential function is also performed to cater for the inadequacy of the English version of a word by using its Yorùbá version in conveying an easily decodable meaning to the listeners which they are likely to be familiar with. The code-mixed expression performing this function is found below.

ICM 1 *And if you *no* get cash, there's no **wàhálà**.*
(And if you don't have cash, there's no problem.)
(UBA 919, YouTube)

The Yorùbá word "wàhálà" which means "problem" is embedded in the code-mixed sentence to enable many listeners easily comprehend the message that there is no network problem with Etisalat and that advertised UBA code solves the problem of lack of cash for customers, thereby performing a referential function.

5.2 Directive function

This function is used by the advertisers to include Yorùbá, English and Naija listeners by switching or mixing Yorùbá, English and Naija languages in order to ensure that different categories of listeners are reached with the intended messages about the advertised products or services. It is discovered that advertisers sometimes switch from one language to another or mix languages together to restate or translate the same message to Yorùbá, English and Naija listeners or convey different messages to these categories of listeners. Also, it is discovered that advertisers switch from one language to another or mix languages to convey the slogans of the advertised products or services so that the English listeners can understand what the advertised products and services stand for or represent.

In addition, another observation is that advertisers oscillate or blend codes to convey some information about the advertised products or services to English, Yorùbá and Naija listeners so that they can have an idea of the information about advertised products and services. This directive function is performed in some code-switched and code-mixed expressions which are found below.

a. Directive Function performed in Inter-sentential Code-switching

ICS 1 *Áyíká tó rewà, ààyè láti ra onírúurú ohun ìsaralóge, ǹnkan èèlò inú ilé, àwọn pẹ̀fúùmù olóòòrùn didùn, oşę ifoşo, ipara lórisirişì àti àwọn oşę iwè, àtásíméńtì, wàini àti provision tó je gidi.*

Pinnacle supermarket is a store where you can get a wide variety of good quality products like perfumes, body cream, soap, provision, cosmetics, weave on and attachments, bathing and laundry products at affordable prices.

(The environment is beautiful and there is the avenue of buying different beauty products, household items, scenting perfumes, laundry soaps, creams of various kinds and bathing soaps, attachments, wine and original provisions.)

(Pinnacle Supermarket, Splash FM, Oyo State)

In the code-switched sentences, the advertiser switched from Yorùbá to English to mention the products available at the supermarket which were earlier listed in Yorùbá and also English language. This code-switching performs a directive function because the advertiser is trying to include the English listeners in the jingle presentation so that they can have the knowledge of the types of products available at Pinnacle Supermarket. Therefore, the code-switching has helped the advertiser to cater for both the Yorùbá and English listeners irrespective of their linguistic or educational background.

ICS 2 One day, you'll be like the sun.

One day, you go shine. (One day, you will shine)

Access, more than banking.

(Access Bank, YouTube)

There is a language oscillation from English in the first sentence to Naija in the second sentence which is to restate a message earlier said in English in Naija so that Naija listeners can be aware of the good wishes and desires of Access Bank for her customers that they shine and become successful in life. This code-switching help to maintain a communication balance between English and Naija listeners so that they can be understand the message being passed across by Access Bank which makes a directive function performed through the code-switching.

b. Directive Function performed in Intra-sentential Code-switching

ICM 1 *Tó bá je èrò iléwọ́ lórisirişì àti èyà ara fòònú, iyeń phone and phone accessories léjèwónléjèwón fún èyin aláratúntà, gbogbo ló yapa sódò wọn.*

(If it is phone and phone accessories in large quantities for retailers, they are all available there.)

(Ade Crystal Concepts Limited, Crown FM, Osun State)

The embedded English words “phone and phone accessories” whose Yorùbá versions “èrò iléwọ́” and “èyà ara fòònú” are earlier mentioned in the code-mixed expression performs a directive function of including the English listeners so that they can have the knowledge of the products the advertised company sells.

ICM 2 *Wón n ta used American spec car, iyeń okò àlòkù òyinbó tówọ́ ò tì dún cargo Nigerian used car, iyeń àlòkù okò eléyìí tó sẹ́ gbókànlé.*

(They are selling used American spec cars, i.e. fairly used cars from abroad which are still intact; cargo Nigerian used cars i.e. Nigerian fairly used cars that are reliable.)

(Great Achievers Automobile Dealers Firm, YouTube)

In the code-mixed sentences, the insertion of the noun phrases “brand new American spec car”, “used American spec car” and “cargo Nigerian used car” occurs to restate the message conveyed to the Yorùbá listeners also to the English listeners so that they can know the types of cars sold by the advertised company. Thus, a directive function is done to include the English listeners in being carried along as regards the types of cars sold by the advertised company. This bridges the communication gap between English and Yorùbá listeners since the types of cars sold are said in English and also explained in Yorùbá in the code-mixed sentences.

ICM 3 *Bákannàà ilèkẹ̀ bèbè oniyinyin yinrin tó je quality wà lódò tiwa fún àwọn obinrin tó gbafe ní gbogbo ojó.*

(Also, shinning waist beads that are of quality are available with us for fashionable women.)

(LaFunky Beauty Skincare, YouTube)

The insertion of the English adjective “quality” is to describe the originality of the waist bead produced by the advertised company so as to make the English listeners have an idea of the high value of the product.

5.3 Expressive function

This function is used by the advertisers to express their feelings, desires, wishes, prayers, request or plea, assurance, superiority of the advertised products or services, confidence and genuineness of information about the advertised products and services or caution about the advertised products or services. In some code-switched, code-mixed and tag switched expressions, expressive functions are used by the advertisers to express various things about the advertised products and services to the listeners which are seen below.

a. Expressive Function performed in Inter-sentential Code-switching

- ICS 1 **Friends go come and friends go go, we no go ever leave you lonely.**
(Friends will come and friends will go, we won't ever leave you lonely.)
 9mobile is here for you o; as you can see, we are here for life.
(9mobile, YouTube)

An expressive function is performed by the advertiser to express the commitment of the advertised network to a long-lasting companionship and service with her customers.

- ICS 2 **Trophy Premium Lager Beer, beer wey dem brew with honour.**
(Trophy Premium Lager Beer, beer that is brewed with honour.)
 Drink responsibly.
(Trophy Premium Lager Beer, Cool FM, Lagos State)

An expressive function is done to express the advertiser's express the advertiser's caution to the listeners to consume the advertised beer with moderation and self-control.

b. Expressive Functions performed in Intra-sentential Code-switching

- ICM 1 **Ókọjá be careful, bo bo bonanza.**
(It's more than be careful, bo bo bonanza.)
(BB Top Solar, New Cruise FM, Ekiti State)

Through the insertion of "be careful" and "bonanza" in the code-mixed sentence, an expressive function is performed which is used to express the authenticity and genuineness of the bonanza or buyers of the advertised solar product to the listeners so that they can be sure that this information is not a sham.

- ICM 2 **Òré mi má lọ fọ, o jẹ sáré lọ 444.**
(My friend don't be deceived, you better quickly use 444.)
(Airtel 444, YouTube)

In the code-mixed sentences, an expressive function is performed through the language mix to express the plea of the advertiser to the listeners to use the code *444#.

c. Expressive Functions performed in Tag Switching

- TGS 1 **Oh my God! bii odidi ojà ilú kan lókè òkun ni.**
(Oh my God! it's like a foreign big market hub.)
(Niyi Shoes, Orange FM, Ondo State)

This English tag inserted is an interjection which is used by the advertiser to express an emotion of amazement at the vast business empire of foreign goods owed by the advertised company.

- TGS 2 **Supa Komando Energy Drink o, ó yá get your own.**
(Supa Komando Energy Drink o, it's time to get your own.)
(Supa Komando Energy Drink, YouTube)

The Yorùbá tag inserted is used to express an appeal to the listeners to buy the advertised drink, thereby performing an expressive function.

5.4 Phatic function

This function of code-switching is used by the advertisers to emphasise and highlight some important words or expressions about the advertised products or services that they want to bring to the attention of the listeners so that it can be registered subconsciously in their minds. Directive function is performed in some code-switched, code-mixed and tag switched expressions. Some of the excerpts performing this function are stated below.

a. Phatic Function performed in Inter-sentential Code-switching

- ICS 1 **Ó yá, ẹ jẹ ká lọ sí Pinnacle tuntun ni Dùgbẹ̀ nílúú Ìbàdàn** for excellent shopping experience.
(Now, let us go to the new Pinnacle Supermarket at Dugbe, Ibadan for an excellent shopping experience)
(Pinnacle Supermarket, Splash FM, Oyo State)

The switch from Yorùbá to English in the codeswitched sentence is done to lay emphasis on the pleasant experience the listeners would have at the new location of Pinnacle Supermarket, thereby performing a phatic function.

ICS 2 *Na who get ear make e hear because you don know wetin you dey miss until you switch, switch.*
(He who has ears should hear because you don't know what you are missing until you switch.)
(Etisalat, YouTube)

A phatic function is performed which is used to stress, emphasise and draw the attention of the listeners to the action of switching to the advertised network in order not to miss out of the benefits Etisalat network offers their customers.

b. Phatic Function performed in Intra-sentential Code-switching

ICM 1 *Tẹ bá ti ri Prestige, kẹ máa ní standard, tori pé ó standard fún ilé tó standard.*
(If you see Prestige, you should call it standard because it is standard for houses that are standard.)
(Prestige Paints, Bond FM, Lagos State)

The phatic function is performed through the repetition of the word “standard” to lay emphasis on the standard quality of the advertised products so that this message can be registered in the listeners’ memory.

ICM 2 *Great Achievers Automobile Dealers Firm ti pé nibi à ñ ta ọkọ lóríşirişì, idí abájo rẹẹ tó fi jẹ wípé confirm lāwọn ọkọ ti wọn.*
(Great Achievers Automobile Dealers Firm has been long in selling vehicles of different types, this is why their vehicles are confirmed.)
(Great Achievers Automobile Dealers Firm, YouTube)

The insertion of the English word “confirm” is used by the advertiser to lay emphasis on the authenticity and quality of the vehicles sold at the advertised company, thereby performing a phatic function.

c. Phatic Function performed in Tag Switching

TGS 1 *Kíákíá, carry your phone now.*
(Quickly, carry your phone now.)
(UBA Magic Banking, YouTube)

TGS 2 *Ó yá, please call *919#.*
(Now, please call *919#.)
(UBA Magic Banking, YouTube)

By embedding the Yorùbá words “kíákíá” which means “quickly” and “ó yá” which means “now”, phatic functions are performed in the tag switched expressions to emphasise and stress on the fast and quick manner at which the advertiser wants the listeners to start using the advertised code (*919#) from UBA for different kinds of transaction.

5.5 Metalinguistic function

This function of code-switching is performed by advertisers when they switch between languages or blend languages to flaunt and showcase their linguistic skills and bilingual proficiency which have a way of impressing the listeners and might make them to be positively disposed towards the advertised products and services. Though these code-switched and code-mixed expressions may perform other functions, the way the advertisers switch and mix the three languages (Yorùbá, Naija and English) together makes them perform a metalinguistic function. Also, this language switch and blend have a way of making the jingle more rhythmical, captivating and memorable to the listeners which helps the intended message of the jingle to easily stick to their memories, thereby influencing them to patronise the advertised products and services. Some excerpts performing these functions are stated below.

a. Metalinguistic Function performed in Inter-sentential Code-switching

ICS 1 Maggi Naija Pot, *delicious bottom pot* made from cray fish, stock fish, smoked fish *make enjoyment no finish.*
(Maggi Naija Pot, a delicious seasoning that gives an African aroma is made from cray fish, stock fish, smoked fish so that enjoyment would not finish.)
(Maggi Naija Pot, YouTube)

The advertiser’s oscillation from English to Naija to English and back to Naija in the code-switched sentence above reflects the linguistic skills and creativity of the advertisers, thereby performing a metalinguistic function. This mode of switch makes the jingle captivating and memorable to the listeners which make the messages about the advertised bank and food seasoning stick easily to the listeners’ memory.

ICS 2 If you see my *gèlè o, e go wound everybody.*
(If you see my headgear, it will defeat everybody’s own)

(Airtel 4G, YouTube)

A metalinguistic function is performed when the advertiser switches from English to Yorùbá and then to Naija within the code-switched sentence which showcases the linguistic skills and ingenuity of the advertiser while passing across information about the superiority of Airtel's 4G network to the listeners.

b. Metalinguistic Functions performed in Intra-sentential Code-switching

ICM 1 And if you **no get** cash, there's no *wàhálà*.

(And if you don't have cash, there's no problem.)

(UBA 919, YouTube)

ICM 2 **Abegi jòó jòó jòó**, dial the number 444.

(I am begging please, please, please; dial the number 444.)

(Airtel 444, YouTube)

The insertion of Yorùbá and Naija words into the English sentences display the multilingual skills of the advertisers while conveying some messages about the advertised bank and network. Therefore, metalinguistic functions are performed in the code-mixed sentences which help the listeners to easily recall the messages of the advertisers.

5.6 Poetic function

This function is performed by the advertiser as puns, rhymes and words from different languages are mixed together to make the jingle entertaining and captivating to the listeners. This makes the message of the jingle more pleasant to the listeners' ears and enables an easy memorisation of the information about the advertised service. A poetic function can be seen in the code-mixed expression below.

ICM 1 **444, ó pò, ó pò, 4 mēta** is a metaphor.

(444, it's plenty, it's plenty, triple 4 is a metaphor.)

(Airtel 444, YouTube)

In the code-mixed sentence, there is the repetition of the Yorùbá word "opo". Also, there is pun in the sentence in which "4 mēta" in Yorùbá sound the same as "metaphor" in English which makes the jingle melodious, pleasant to the ears and entertaining as words from both languages rhyme together to produce a harmonious sound, thereby performing a poetic function.

5.6 Maintenance function

This is a new function that is discovered during the analysis of the data which is not part of the six functions of code-switching by Appel and Muysken (2006). This function of code-switching is reflected when advertisers code-switch or code-mix in order to achieve the following things:

a. Maintenance function is performed to mention and maintain the brand names or part of the brand names of advertised products and services. In the excerpts below, the English brand names of the advertised products and services are embedded within the Yorùbá sentences because they represent the names of the advertised products and services whose nomenclature and unique identity must be maintained. These English brand names are emboldened in the code-mixed expressions which are seen below.

ICM 1 **Brother George Honey**, gbogbo èniyàn, ẹ máa ràá o.

(Brother George Honey, everybody should buy it.)

(Brother George Honey, Adaba FM, Ondo State)

ICM 2 **Dàgbà, kóo lágbára kóo sì jáfáfá pèlú milliki idàgbàsókè Peak 456.**

(Grow, be strong and smart with developmental milk Peak 456)

(Peak 456 Milk, Splash FM, Oyo State)

ICM 3 **Şe ẹ ti wá rii pé ògá ni LaFunky Beauty Skincare** ń se ní gbogbo ojò pátá.

(Have you now seen that LaFunky Beauty Skincare is superior to others at all times.)

(LaFunky Beauty Skincare, YouTube)

ICM 4 **Great Achievers Automobile Dealers Firm** ti pé nibi à ń ta ọkọ lóríşiríşì, idí abájo rèè tó fi jé wipé **confirm** làwọn ọkọ ti wọn.

(Great Achievers Automobile Dealers Firm has been long in selling vehicles of different types, this is why their vehicles are confirmed.)

(Great Achievers Automobile Dealers Firm, YouTube)

b. Maintenance function is performed to mention and maintain the names of organisational bodies the advertised products and services are attached to or belong to and or those organisational bodies who endorse and approve of the advertised products and services. In the excerpts below, the English names or acronyms of the organisational bodies are

embedded in the Yorùbá sentences to maintain their names and identities in the jingle presentation. The code-mixed expressions performing this function can be seen below.

- ICM 1 *Ìgbìmò SON ti fún wọn lámi èyè NIS Mark of Standard.*
(The SON body has given them an NIS Mark of Standard award.)
(Prestige Paints, Bond FM, Lagos State)
- ICM 2 *È máa gbàgbe o, pèlú irànlówò Napoleon Mesh Land Easy Buy, iyekiye tó n bẹ lówó rẹ ni kóo wá san sí IAS.*
(Don't forget, with the help of Napoleon Mesh Land Easy Buy, come and pay any amount with you to IAS.)
(Napoleon Mesh Land Easy Buy, Splash FM, Ogun State)
- ICM 3 *Ìwọ ni idánwò WAEC ni o, NECO ni o, UTME ni o àti gbogbo àwọn idánwò jànkànjànkàn, bíbójẹ ni àwọn akékòjò Best Results International School n bó àwọn idánwò wònyí jẹ bí ẹni n bó ẹyin jẹ.*
(Be it exams like WAEC, NECO, UTME and other tough external examinations, Best Results International School students pass these exams easily without difficulty.)
(Best Results International School, Crown FM, Osun State.)
- ICM 4 *Ìdí niyí tí Standard Organisation of Nigeria fi fi òntẹ lu, ti Nigerian Electrical Contractors náà fi dibò fún.*
(This is why the Standard Organisation of Nigeria approve it and Nigerian Electrical Contractors choose it.)
(Joykem Wires and Cables, Splash FM, Oyo State)
- ICM 5 *Owó ceramic filter kéré ju isẹ rẹ lọ, bánkì àgbáyé àti àjà World Health Organisation (W.H.O) fowó síi.*
(The price of ceramic filter is smaller than its work, the World Bank and World Health Organisation (W.H.O) endorses it.)
(Omilero International, YouTube)

c. Maintenance function is performed to maintain the brand names advertised companies give to their products and services. In the excerpts below, the English names of the products and services of the advertised companies are embedded within the Yorùbá sentences in order to preserve their unique identities and given names. There are some examples of code-switched and code-mixed expressions performing this function below.

- ICS 1 *Ètò òhún ná pè ní "just call us, just call us.*
(The programme is called "just call us, just call us.)
(Topsilas Ozonised Water, Orisun FM, Osun State)
- ICM 1 *Àimoye òdà ni wón ẹ láti ilé-isẹ wón, ẹ polongo prestige decorative paint, Prestige plus, prestige test coat, prestige emulsion, prestige wood finish, prestige floor filler, prestige marine coat.*
(Different paints are made by their company, announce them like prestige decorative paint, prestige plus, prestige test coat, prestige emulsion, prestige wood finish, prestige floor filler, prestige marine coat.)
(Prestige Paints, Bond FM, Lagos State)
- ICM 2 *Gbogbo ẹni tó fẹ ra Profit City tí à n tà ní 300,000 naira báyii àti First Class City tí à n tà ní 250,000 naira báyii, 100,000 naira péré lè ra pilòtì kan bá ẹ tà nìgbà ẹdínwó.*
(All those who want to buy Profit City that we are selling for 300,000 naira now and First-Class City that we are selling for 250,000 naira now, you would buy 1 plot for 100,000 naira only as it was sold during promo.)
(Napoleon Mesh Land Easy Buy, Splash FM, Ogun State)
- ICM 3 *Àsé àràmondà, Àsé iyanu tí n ẹ gbogbo idòtì inú omi pátápátá porogodo ceramic filter; ceramic filter ní ẹ omi kadara tí gbogbo bacteria yóò kànjàngbòn t'ómi mimu wa yóò fi wá lókànbalẹ pèsẹ.*
(An amazing and wonderful filter that filter all the dirt inside water is ceramic filter; ceramic filter filters water so that bacteria will be in trouble and your drinking water will give you rest of mind.)
(Omilero International, YouTube)
- ICM 4 *Nínú LaFunky seeti láti šalábàà pàdé LaFunky Whitening Scrub, LaFunky Moisturizer Lotion, LaFunky Morning Face Cream, LaFunky Night Face Cream, LaFunky Body Cream, Carrot Oil pèlú Whitening Oil atunrase.*
(Inside LaFunky set, you will see LaFunky Whitening Scrub, LaFunky Moisturizer Lotion, LaFunky Morning Face Cream, LaFunky Night Face Cream, LaFunky Body Cream, Carrot Oil with Whitening Oil that rejuvenates the body.)
(LaFunky Beauty Skincare, YouTube)

5.7 Elaborative function

This is another new function that is discovered during the analysis of the data which is not part of the functions of code-switching by Appel and Muysken (2006). This function of code-switching is performed when advertisers switch from one language to another to elaborate and give further details and additional information on what was earlier stated about the advertised products and services in the code-switched expressions. This function is performed only in Inter-sentential Code-switching. Some excerpts performing this function are stated below.

ICS 1 All I ask in return is that you treat me a little better with Hypo Toilet Cleaner.

My hygiene na your own o. (My Hygiene is your own hygiene.)
(Hypo Toilet Cleaner, YouTube)

An elaborative function of code-switching is performed through the language switch to make the listeners understand the reason why they should clean their toilets with the advertised product because the state of its cleanliness determines their own health and wellbeing.

ICS 2 *Adron dey do wonders. (Adron is doing wonders)*

Yes, this season, Adron Homes is giving 10 to 40% discount on all landed properties, subscribers will also get promo giveaways like cow, goat, 50kg bag of rice, vegetable oil and seasoning packs when they pay.
(Adron Homes, YouTube)

Through the language switch, an elaborative function of code-switching is performed for the give further explanation and elaboration on the wonders Adron Homes is said to be doing which is offering of promo giveaways of food items and consumables to her customers.

ICS 3 *2Sure, no be wash oh, no be wash oh.*

(2sure is not just an ordinary washing liquid.)

Use 2Sure dishwashing liquid, available in 2Sure Original and 2Sure fresh lemon in 250ml, 500ml and 1000ml sizes.

(2sure Dishwashing Liquid, YouTube)

The language alternation is done to elaborate and give additional information about the types of advertised product and their sizes which performs an elaborative function.

ICS 4 *No need to dey worry, Qwik.ng dey.*

(No need to be worried, there is Qwik.ng.)

When you download, you sell; when you download, you buy.

(Qwik.ng, YouTube)

An elaborative function is performed through the language switch to give the listeners more details and explanation that the advertised online marketplace reduces the burden of people because they can buy and sell on this platform.

ICS 5 **919# call am now. (*919# call it now.)*

Get started with UBA magic banking to receive or send money, pay bills, buy airtime, check your account balance and open an account instantly.

(UBA Magic Banking, YouTube)

An elaborative function of code-switching is performed whereby the advertiser uses the language switch to elaborate and give further information about the different transactions the advertised code (*919#) can be used for by the listeners.

ICS 6 *Na 10 gigabyte data just land my Airtel so. (It's 10 gigabyte data that just entered my Airtel.)*

Guess how much? 3000 naira.

(Airtel, Cool FM, Lagos State)

An elaborative function is performed through the language switch to give further information on the amount required to get the 10gb data on Airtel which is ₦3000 so as to make the listeners have a full information about the amount the data offer from the advertised network can be bought.

6. Findings and discussions

From the analysis of the advertisement jingles, the code-switched, code-mixed and tag switched expressions used by advertisers perform the six (6) functions of code-switching by Appel and Musyken (Appel & Musyken, 2006). Apart from the six (6) functions of code-switching by Appel and Muysken performed in the code-switched, code-mixed and tag switched expressions, two (2) other functions are discovered which are called Maintenance Function and Elaborative Function.

It performs a Directive Function to include and identify with different categories of listeners so that they can be carried along with the intended messages of the jingle. Also, it performs a Referential Function to cater for the lack of facility or inadequacy of a language to express some words and concepts and also to make provision for inadequacy of the translated versions or equivalents of some words in a language in conveying a straightforward and easily decodable meaning. In addition, it performs an Expressive Function to express and convey feelings, assurance, commitment, plea or caution about advertised products or services.

Moreover, a Phatic Function is performed to emphasise, highlight or repeat some important words or expressions that the advertisers want the listeners to remember and take note of about the advertised products or services. Also, a Metalinguistic Function is performed to display the advertisers' linguistic skills and bilingual proficiency which leaves an impressive mark on the listeners and make them positively disposed towards the advertiser and the advertised products and services. It also makes the jingle rhythmical, captivating and memorable, thereby producing a mnemonic effect on the listeners about the advertised products and services. Additionally, a Poetic Function is performed when advertisers use words that sound the same from various languages, thereby making the jingle entertaining, amusing and catchy to the listeners.

The other two (2) other functions different from the six (6) functions of code-switching by Appel and Muysken (2006) are called Maintenance Function and Elaborative Function. As regards the Maintenance Function, in the process of advertising products and services in jingles, it is discovered that the advertisers mention and maintain the English brand names of the advertised products and services within Yorùbá sentences. Also, they maintain the names of organisational bodies the advertised products and services belong to or are approved of. In addition, advertisers maintain the brand names advertised companies give to their products and services. Therefore, Maintenance Function is performed to maintain and preserve the English brand names of the advertised products and services and organisational bodies and their unique identities within Yorùbá sentences when presenting the jingle.

On the other hand, Elaborative Function is performed when advertisers switch from one language to other to elaborate and give further details and additional information on what was earlier stated about the advertised products and services in the code-switched expressions. All these functions enhance the listeners' acceptability, understanding and positive disposal towards the products and services.

7. Conclusion and recommendation

Code-switching and code-mixing are not displayed as a sign of linguistic deficiency and incompetence by the advertisers but rather, they are linguistic skills and strategies employed by advertisers to purposely achieve some socially motivated functions in order to effectively convey the intended messages about products and services to the public. These functions of code-switching performed have a way of contributing to achieving the ultimate goal of advertising which is to increase sales of products and services and maximise profit in business. It is therefore recommended that advertisers view and employ the linguistic tools of code-switching and code-mixing in different advertising engagements because they are genuine and potent tools which can guarantee a very successful transfer of information about products and services to the members of the society so that this process would not be futile and just a waste of time.

8. Funding

This research paper received no internal or external funding

9. Acknowledgments

I hereby acknowledge my supervisor, Prof. E.T. Babalola who has assiduously supervised this study to fruition. Also, the assistance of my research assistants who helped in the collection of jingles are also appreciated.

ORCID

Mary Temiloluwa Oso <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-0342-0606>

Emmanuel Taiwo Babalola <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-0211-2671>

Moses Chika Christian-Achinihu <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-4266-3549>

References

- Akindele, F., & Adegbite, W. (1999). *The sociology and politics of English in Nigeria: An introduction*. O.A.U. Press
- Almoaily, M. (2023). Code-switching functions in online advertisements on Snapchat. *Plos One*, 18(7).
- Amjad, S., & Rehman, S. U. (2020). Code switching and code mixing in multilingual societies: A case of Pakistan. *Sci.Int.(Lahore)*, 32(6), 655-659.
- Appel, R., & Muysken, P. (1987). (1st ed.). *Language contact and bilingualism*. University Press.
- Appel, R., & Muysken, P. (2006). (4th ed.). *Language contact and bilingualism*. University Press.
- Babalola, E., & Taiwo, R. (2009). Code-switching in Nigerian hip-hop music. In E. Babalola & T. Azeez (Eds.), *Critical perspectives on language, literature and communication studies: Festschrift in honour of Siyan Oyeweso* (pp. 55-66). OAU Press.
- Bamisaye, T. O. (2007). The manifestation of code-switching and code-mixing in broadcasting in Nigeria. *Papers in English and Linguistics*, 7 & 8.

- Banatao, M. B., & Malenab-Temporal, C. (2018). Code-switching in television advertisements. *TESOL International Journal*, 13(4), 121-136
- Barnali, C. (2017). Code-switching and mixing in communication: A study on language contact in Indian media. *Research Association for Interdisciplinary Studies*. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3085969>
- Chan, B. H. S. (2009). Code-switching between typologically distinct languages. In B.E. Bullock & A.J. Toribio (Eds.), *The Cambridge handbook of linguistic code-switching* (pp. 182-198). Cambridge University Press.
- Chiu, M. (2012). Code-switching and identity constructions in Taiwan TV commercials. *台灣學誌*, 4, 27-49.
- Eleshin-Ajikobi, A. F. (2025). Olùkùmi polar question derivation: A complex linguistic inquiry. *Journal of Languages, Linguistics and Literary Studies*, 5 (1), 1 – 26
- Fitri, N., & Pamungkas, A. D. (2023). The use of code switching and code mixing by Indofood and Unilever food advertisements on television. *Inference: Journal of English Language Teaching*, 5(3), 251-260.
- Garcia, D. V. (2020). English and Tagalog: *A study of code switching in Philippine television Advertisements* [Bachelors Project, Goteborgs Universitet].
- Girsang, M. L. (2015). An analysis of code switching and code mixing as found in television advertisement. *The Explora Journal of English Language Teaching (ELT) and Linguistics*, 1712072009.
- Gocheo, P. (2013). Code-switching in Television-mediated political campaign ads in the Philippines. *Philippine ESL Journal*, 10, 30-55.
- Gumperz, J. J. (1982). *Discourse strategies*. Cambridge University Press.
- Herman, Thao, N.V., Purba R., & Simanjunta, N. S. U. (2022). Attracting viewers through advertisement by using code mixing: A sociolinguistics study. *Anglophile Journal*, 2(2), 80-88.
- Hsu, J. (2008). Glocalization and English mixing in advertising in Taiwan: Its discourse domains, linguistic patterns, cultural constraints, localized creativity and socio-psychological effects. *Journal of Creative Communications*, 3(2), 155-183
- Hoffman, C. (1991). *An introduction to bilingualism*. Longman.
- Jayeola, W. A., & Adeniyi, K. (2025). Parameter setting and feature mismatch in a Yoruba-English bilingual child. *Journal of Languages, Linguistics and Literary Studies (JLLLS)*, 5(2), 95-107.
- Kartika, R. (2017, June 17). *Motivation for code-switching in cosmetics television advertising in Indonesia* (Paper presentation). The Fifth Undergraduate Conference on ELT, Linguistics, and Literature. Yogyakarta, Indonesia.
- Khan, A. M. (2014). Social aspects of code-switching: An analysis of Pakistani television advertisements. *Information Management and Business Review*, 6(6), 269-279
- Lanz Vallejo, L. (2011). *El cambio de código español-inglés como creatividad lingüística y presentación de la imagen en tweets escritos por tijuaneños*, http://www.cucsh.uan.edu.mx/jornadas/modulos/memoria/lanz_cambio_codigo.
- Lee, J.S. (2006). Linguistic constructions of modernity: English mixing in Korean television commercials. *Language in society*, 35(1).
- Mainake, E. (2021). Code-switching on advertisement: A case of food advertisements in Indonesia. *Huele: Journal of Applied Linguistics, Literature and Culture*, 1(1), 41-52.
- Mulyanto, A., Warsiti, S., & Dewi, R. O. (2023). Advertising media, an analysis of code in compilation of food and beverage ads on YouTube. *Journal of Pragmatics and Discourse Research*, 3(2), 203-217.
- Muslimah, I., Ramendra, D. P., & Agustini, D. A. E. (2016). An analysis of codeswitching used in advertisement at Guntur radio, Singaraja. *Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa Inggris Undiksha*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.23887/jpbi.v4i2.8730>
- Myers-Scotton, C. (1979). Code-switching as a safe choice in choosing a lingua franca. In W.C. McCormack & S.A. Wurm (Eds.), *Language and society: Anthropological issues*. (pp. 71-88). <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110806489.71>
- Ogunremi, J. O. (1992). Code-switching: A great threat to the teaching and learning of the Nigerian languages. *Dougirei- Journal of Education*, 2, 52-57.
- Ogunsiji, Y. (2013). The inevitability of language interlarding among bilinguals. In A. Ogunsiji, A. Kehinde & A. Odebunmi (Eds.), *Language, literature and discourse* (pp. 381-392). Stirling-Horden Publishers Ltd.
- Poplack, S. (1980). Sometimes I'll start a sentence in Spanish y termino el español!: Toward a typology of code-switching. *Linguistics*, 18, 581-618.
- Raden, N., Ainis, Alquratu, S., Putri, S., Aprianty, A., Cici, K., & Kusnaryati, F. (2022). Code-switching and code-mixing on Japanese television advertising. *Central Asia & the Caucasus*, 23(1), 3866-3873.
- Riaz, M. (2019). Language variation: Code-mixing and code-switching in Pakistani commercials. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 15(2), 411-419.
- Rosmiaty, R., & Muhri, A. (2020). Investigating code-mixing as persuasive strategies in advertising: A study of code-mixing in Indonesian commercial context. *ELT Worldwide*, 7(1), 69-76.
- Rusli, W. S., Shaari, A. H., Zainuddin, S. Z., Shi, N. L., & Amin, A. S. (2018). Intra and inter-sentential code-switching phenomena in modern Malay songs. *The Southeast Asian Journal of English Language Studies*, 24(3), 184-205.
- Singh, P., & Mishra, S. (2021). Marketing strategy of mixing another language in adverts: Study of English code-mixing and code-switching in Indian advertisements for cold drinks. *Psychology and Education*. 58(1), 2168-2179.
- Tajolosa, T. D. (2013). Motivations for code-switching in advertising and the construction of consumers' multiple identities: The case of Philippine TV commercials. *Philippine ESL Journal*, 11, 48-85.
- Toribio, A. J. (2001). On the emergence of bilingual code-switching competence. *Bilingualism: Language and Cognition*, 4(3), 203-231.

- Wirajaya, P., Suarnajaya, W., & Mahendrayana, G. (2023). The analysis of Indonesian-English code mixings used in the advertisements of Guntur radio FM station Bali. *International Journal of Language and Literature*, 7(1), 44-52.
- Yankova, D., & Vassileva, I. (2013). Functions and mechanisms of code-switching in Bulgarian Canadians. *Etudes Canadiennes/Canadian Studies*, 74, 103-121.
- Younes, M. (2017). *Code choice in Egyptian TV advertisements*. [Master's Thesis, American University, Cairo].

